

STUDYING NON-EQUIVALENT VOCABULARY IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the problems of transferring non-equivalent legal vocabulary in translation from English into Russian, reveals the concept of “non-equivalent vocabulary”, and considers ways of translating non-equivalent vocabulary using the example of the terminology of professions. The main methods of transmitting non-equivalent vocabulary are tracing, transliteration, description; a combination of tracing and descriptive methods is often used, while the choice of method for translating non-equivalent vocabulary depends on the context.

Key words and phrases: non-equivalent vocabulary; translation; legal English; legal terms; transmission methods; context.

The process of globalization, which is characteristic of modern society, covers all spheres of public life and contributes to the expansion of political, trade, economic, scientific, and cultural relations between different countries. Active cooperation between countries and international tourism lead to increased mobility of people and more frequent conduct of business through the global information network.

In this regard, the need for translation as a means of facilitating communication between people speaking different languages is constantly increasing. A special place in this is occupied by the translation of texts. Due to the growing importance of translation activities, translation problems arise that are associated with differences in cultures, realities, and traditions of different countries. This fact determines the relevance and practical significance of this work. The purpose of the article is to analyze ways of transmitting non-equivalent vocabulary in translation from English into Russian.

Non-equivalent vocabulary – lexical units of the source language (see Source language) or dialect that do not have regular (full or partial) dictionary

correspondences in the target language. E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G.Kostomarov¹ define the layer of non-equivalent vocabulary as “words whose content plan cannot be compared with any foreign language lexical concepts.”

The category of non-equivalent vocabulary primarily includes words denoting specific objects and phenomena in the life of a given cultural and linguistic community - realities and historicisms.

Non-equivalent vocabulary includes words designated by the term “реалия” or “слово-реалия”. For example, Ya.I.Retzker² writes about non-equivalent vocabulary, which is primarily a designation of realities characteristic of the country of the source language. Words-realities are an integral part of the vocabulary of the folk language and represent one of the means of expressing national and historical flavor in works of art. The term “реалия” means “... elements of the life and culture of a historical era and social system, government structure and folklore of a given people, alien to other peoples.” For effective equivalent translation, it is very useful for the translator to have an idea of the reason for lexical non-equivalence.

Non-equivalent language units can be divided into several subgroups:

- proper names: Конёк-Горбунок, Сивка-Бурка, Иванушка-дурачок, Жар-птица, Тулпар (баш.), Акбузат (баш.), Урал-Батыр (баш.), Шурале (баш.);
- clothes, shoes, jewelry: кафтан, лапти, калоши, тюбетейка (баш.), чалма (баш.);
- buildings and objects of traditional (folk) life: изба, хата, терем, ухват, кочерга, лавка, сундук, баня, сани, коромысло, самовар, юрта (баш.);
- traditions, holidays, rituals: Масленица, Пасха, Рождество, Сабантуй (баш.), Курбан (баш.);
- musical instruments: гусли, гармонь, балалайка, курай (баш.), кубыз (баш.);
- mythological and fairy-tale creatures: чудо-юдо, колобок, домовой, чёрт, леший, русалка, водяной, вурдалак, батыр (баш.), шайтан (баш.);

¹ Костомаров В.Н. Язык и культура: Лингвострановедение в преподавании русского языка как иностранного. – М., 1983

² Ретцер, Я. И. Теория перевода и переводческая практика : очерки лингвистической теории перевода. — М. : Междунар. отношения, 1974. — 216 с.

- food and drinks: щи, каша, борщ, квас, кумыс (баш.), айран (баш.), корот (баш.), катык (баш.), бишбармак (баш.), баурсак (баш.);
- words from folklore: петрушка, скomorox, ряженые, колядки;
- religious terms and concepts: икона, крест, таинство, успение, соборование, мулла (баш.), мечеть (баш.), никах (баш.);
- folk games, toys: матрёшка, лапта, горелки, хоровод, жмурки³.

Consider the following example:

“his very ancient family had been noted, time out of mind, for a peculiar sensibility of temperament”⁴ - “род его очень древний, и все Ашеры с незапамятных времен отличались необычайной утонченностью чувств”.

In this case, the translator was faced with the problem of translating such a lexical phenomenon as an idiom. According to the Explanatory Dictionary, a phraseological fusion, or idiom, is a semantically indivisible phrase, the meaning of which is completely undeducible from the meanings of its constituent components; their semantic independence is completely lost. To more accurately convey the meaning of an idiom, the translator resorts to the method of selecting a phraseological analogue. Such a non-equivalent can be classified as a random type.

Let's move on to the next example:

The body having been encoffined - “The body was placed in a coffin even earlier”.

This sample is a striking example of structural exoticism. Thus, the Russian language does not have sufficient means for a compact description of this action, so the translator used the technique of explication. So, the translator replaces the verb to uncoffin with the phrase “put in a coffin.”

There are several features in the process of teaching non-equivalent vocabulary. Firstly, there is no such stage as translating the word into the native language of foreign students. This is due to the fact that non-equivalent words do not have stable

³ Муллагалиева Л. К., Саяхова Л. Г. Русский язык в диалоге культур: пособие для учителя. Уфа: Китап, 2008. 208 с

⁴ <https://poestories.com/read/houseofusher>.

correspondences in other languages. Secondly, it is impossible to carry out work on the selection of synonyms, since they are missing for the same reason.

Non-equivalent words can be borrowed into foreign languages, since any language needs a layer of lexical units denoting the realities of a foreign culture. “Нужные слова” are assimilated into other languages, such as the borrowed words парламент, ацтеки, пончо in Russian.

However, many words that do not belong to the categories of realities and historicisms also do not have complete equivalents in other languages.

This is due to differences in denotative or connotative semantics. For example, the Russian nouns *девочка* and *девушка*, on the one hand, and their English equivalent *girl*, on the other, differ in the scope of meaning. A reverse example: the two English words *bank* “*берег реки*” and *shore* “*берег моря*” in Russian correspond to one word *shore*. This pattern covers not only nouns: for example, the Russian language distinguishes two colors in the color spectrum – *синий* and *голубой*, while both designations are part of the national language. In many other languages of the world they correspond to one word each.

In general, translating all types of non-equivalent vocabulary is considered an extremely difficult problem, since the translator always faces the problem of choice. Preservation of the internal form can lead to a violation in pragmatics, and the preservation of pragmatic meaning can be accompanied by the loss of reference, i.e., a certain part of the meaning. This choice cannot be fixed by any universal translation norm, but is based only on the degree of skill and taste of the translator.

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